

Evaluation of Learning Modules Based on the TPACK Framework to Increase Student Understanding in Learning

^{*1}Slamet Kurniawan Fahrurrozi, ²Cucuk Wawan Budiyanto, ¹Muhammad Hassan Massaty

¹Information Technology Study Program, NEST Polytechnic, Sukoharjo, Indonesia

²Informatics Education Department, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Universitas Sebelas Maret, Surakarta, Indon

Corresponding Email: slametkfrozi@gmail.com

Abstract:

The objective of this research is to examine three aspects: (1) the implementation of learning modules that utilize the TPACK (Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge) framework, (2) the impact of using TPACK-based learning modules on students' understanding, and (3) students' reactions to learning modules based on the TPACK framework. This research method employs a descriptive-evaluative approach that is qualitative in nature. Qualitative research utilizes data that is expressed through words, narratives, and information provided by informants. The feasibility of implementation was measured using Likert scale instruments, understanding was measured by pre-test and post-test questions, and student responses were analyzed through interviews. The participants in this study consisted of 33 students enrolled in the Informatics and Computer Engineering Education program at Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta. According to the research findings, it can be inferred that the implementation of the learning module falls under the "excellent" category. Therefore, it may be considered as a viable choice for teaching materials in the E-Business Technology course. (2) Student comprehension has significantly improved, with the average score rising from 71.9 to 87.87. (3) Feedback from interviews indicated that students found the module to be helpful and easily comprehensible as a teaching resource. However, there were still certain aspects that required adjustment in order to optimize the TPACK-based module. The TPACK framework enhances the dissemination of content that is characterized by a systematic, comprehensive, and conceptual approach. This study has presented a novel perspective that suggests the TPACK framework can be utilized to enhance learning outcomes.

Keywords: *TPACK; Learning Module; E-business Technology.*

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Introduction

Advances in science and technology require changes in all aspects of people's lives. The changes that occur in people's lives also affect the field of education, including changes to the curriculum and ongoing learning. Competent human resources are essential to navigate and anticipate the evolving demands in education and the workforce. The aims, methods, materials, and experiences in learning activities should align with students' needs to prepare them for current and future challenges (Munir, 2012). Considering the diverse needs of students is crucial for achieving optimal learning. Teachers as educators are the figures who socialize and interact with students the most compared to other personnel in the school who feel the need to understand these needs. The task of educators is to make learning plans and carry out the teaching and learning process, carry out learning assessments, guide and train students, research and study, and communicate with the community (Sagala, 2013). Because of this, teachers as educators need to improve their abilities.

Educators have an important role in delivering optimal teaching materials. A conducive learning system and an environment that supports the learning process is needed to achieve success in educational goals (Sihombing et al., 2024). Teaching can be interpreted as an effort to create a system and environment that can enable the learning process to take place (Lubis, 2021). Educators have an obligation to be competent in their field, so that the knowledge or information conveyed by educators is correct and on target, with the aim of teaching and learning activities having material content that is appropriate (pedagogical) to the nature of learning. The essence of learning is a process of expanding knowledge (Content), skills, and self-interaction with various information and the environment. This aspect is known as Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK).

Mishra and Koehler (Koehler & Mishra, 2009), define Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) as pedagogical content knowledge (science of education) identifying parts of the material according to the pedagogical (art of educating) educators. Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) is a combination of pedagogical and content aspects. PCK includes how educators understand topics or problems and issues that are systematic, represented and harmonized with the different abilities and interests of students, and provided understanding in the form of instructions. Huda (Huda et al., 2017) revealed that the role of PCK in delivering material is very important for prospective educators. Prospective educators (pre-service teachers) need to have the ability to identify PCK (Fariyani et al., 2020). Educators are required to have an adequate understanding of the material to be taught and the ways or methods by which the material will be taught to students. Abd-El-Khalick (Abd-El-Khalick, 2013) observations stated that there are at least 2 transformation components that are directly related to content knowledge, such as interpreting the ideas to be conveyed and representing or conveying these ideas. PCK has been developed by researchers which is more popular with the term TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge). Research by Susan Marie Cox (Cox, 2008) provides an illustration that TPACK is a framework whose component construction consists of technological content knowledge (TCK), technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK), and TPACK itself (the central component of the framework listed previously).

TPACK has important components for prospective teachers (pre-service teachers) to improve teaching competence, plan learning plans and their relationship to the use of digital technology (Schmid & Garrels, 2021). 21st century learning with the modern era now requires the ability to communicate, collaborate and use technology in the teaching and learning process. According to Brun & Hinojosa (Brun & Hinojosa, 2014), integrating ICT in the development of the teaching and learning process has a positive impact in the form of a significant contribution to the level of learning practice on students. Educators are required to have IT literacy skills in the teaching and learning process with various learning methods and approaches in the classroom (Ertmer & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2010; Webb & Robinson Kapavik, 2015). The latest research produced by Rosenberg & Kohler (Rosenberg & Koehler, 2015), explains that learning in the 21st century can achieve success by integrating aspects of understanding material, learning methods, and the use of information technology in learning. To increase creativity, accountability and collaboration in the learning process, it can be linked to TPACK (Kutaka-Kennedy, 2015). Yazdani & Godbole (Yazdani & Godbole, 2014) explained that the positive contribution of learning that is carried out well can increase students' motivation to excel and improve other academic abilities. Mourlam (Mourlam, 2017) said that when entering the profession, educators are expected to prepare students' skills as keys to the 21st century by using digital technology.

Digital technology needs to be developed further not only as teaching material, but to support educators in carrying out learning. According to Valtonen et al., (Valtonen et al., 2017) 21st century abilities are expected to have the skills needed to collaborate, as a problem solver, creative and innovative thinking and the ability to utilize Computer Information Technology (ICT) as a teaching medium. Keengwe et al., (Keengwe et al., 2009) said that although technology plays an important role in implementing learning, educators must also design appropriate learning environments that effectively combine technology to help students learn well with technology. Apart from that, Irmak & Tüzün (Irmak & Yılmaz Tüzün, 2019) said that understanding the knowledge felt by prospective educators in

teaching is more important as preparing prospective educators for their future careers. TPACK is an integrative type and transformation of prospective educators' knowledge necessary for the effective use of ICT in the classroom (Chai et al., 2013). The importance of digital technology has penetrated all aspects of life starting from agriculture, e-business, transportation, education, and many more. E-business technology is one of the challenges that will continue to be needed in the future. Vivianti (Vivianti, 2012) saw this gap and analyzed technology material with a teaching module. The development of modules as teaching media is considered very effective for integrating with certain values (Anin, 2019). For this reason, there are still many opportunities and challenges for the module to be developed as an effective teaching medium for E-business technology.

The limited integration of e-business technology modules into learning models highlights an opportunity to enhance student competencies in this critical field. Current learning strategies often rely on conventional approaches, underscoring the need for innovative and engaging methods. There are many models that can be integrated into teaching media (Bajracharya, 2021). One of the models that offers a complete learning concept is TPACK. The application of the TPACK concept to the e-business technology module will have a big impact and complete components that can measure the expected student competency.

The application of the TPACK concept to learning opens avenues for research into its effectiveness in enhancing educational outcomes and integrating technology into various subjects. Educators have the opportunity to integrate the TPACK concept into their teaching media, especially the use of E-Business technology modules. Therefore, this research aims to evaluate the implementation of the integration of the TPACK concept in the E-Business Technology learning module for information and computer engineering education students.

Research Method

This research uses a qualitative approach. Data processing for factual information in the field is carried out descriptively-evaluatively. The data used in qualitative research is presented in the form of words, narratives, and information from informants. TPACK achievements by Computer Engineering Education students are explored in depth, in detail and sorted well according to findings in the field without changing the facts that influence each other on the research variables.

Activities carried out in this research include integrating E-Business Technology modules by applying the TPACK model, implementing learning modules, collecting data, and analyzing data. Data analysis in this research uses descriptive-evaluative analysis. The focus of the research is more on the analysis of TPACK integration in the implementation of learning modules in learning E-business Technology courses in the Informatics and Computer Engineering Education Study Program.

Data Collection Techniques and Instruments

This study aimed to comprehensively evaluate the learning process and assess the effectiveness of the implemented learning modules. To achieve this, data were collected using three primary techniques: questionnaires, interviews, and documentation. The questionnaire assessed TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) by gathering self-reported data on participants' proficiency in Technological Pedagogy (TP), Content Knowledge (CK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), and their intersections (TPK, PCK, TCK, and TPACK). The instrument used to gather this data, which is shown in Table 1 below, was adapted from the work of Schmidt-Crawford, Baran, Thompson, and Mishra (Schmidt et al., 2009), ensuring that responses could be systematically analyzed for insights into the module's effectiveness in enhancing TPACK-related competencies.

In addition to the questionnaires, interviews were conducted to validate and explore the data obtained from respondents. Researchers employed unstructured interviews, allowing for a conversational approach guided by a list of predetermined questions (Gall et al., 2003). This method provided flexibility in capturing students' responses and attitudes toward the learning modules, specifically focusing on their TPACK skill development. Documentation, including RPS (Lesson Plan) documents, module artifacts, and other materials, provided authentic evidence supporting the analysis of the study's objectives. These documents, together with the questionnaire and interview data, enabled a comprehensive analysis, offering a holistic view of the learning process and the effectiveness of the modules in addressing the research problem.

Table 1. Instrument grid

Indicators	Sub-Indicators	Question Items
Content Knowledge	Students master the material taught	4
Pedagogical Knowledge	Take reflective action to improve the quality of learning	3

Pedagogical Content Knowledge	Provide questions to measure students' understanding of the material being taught	4
Tecnological Knowledge	Master the technology used well	7
Technological Content Knowledge	The technology used is relevant to the material taught	3
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	Using computer and smartphone applications in learning	3
Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge	Combining business knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technological knowledge to create effective learning	3

Result and Discussion

After the learning module was utilized, feedback was collected from 33 students, the primary target audience for the E-Business Technology course. The responses indicate a highly positive reception, with students emphasizing the module's relevance and appropriateness as a teaching tool. According to the questionnaire results, students felt the module effectively supported their learning process, with clear and engaging content that made the subject matter more accessible. The overall evaluation from students in various categories rated the module as "very good," underscoring its role in enhancing the quality of classroom learning. These responses reflect a general consensus that the module contributes significantly to their understanding of E-Business Technology concepts, making it a valuable asset in the learning environment.

Result

To further assess the module's effectiveness, researchers observed classroom activities while students engaged with the module content. It was noted that learning activities flowed smoothly and adhered to the objectives outlined in the module, allowing students to develop their skills through direct, hands-on practice. This alignment between module structure and classroom practice enabled students to implement the theoretical knowledge presented in the module. One notable feature was the use of barcodes linked to online resources, allowing students to explore supplemental materials on the internet for a more comprehensive understanding. This feature received positive feedback, as students found it a practical tool for enhancing their knowledge. One student shared, "In my opinion, the module used is good; the sentences are not complicated. With the QR Code, we can explore more extensive material on YouTube and articles—a fun, new learning experience" (31 March 2020, Zoom Meet, 19.00-21.00 WIB). This integration of technology helped bridge in-class learning with independent exploration, fostering a more dynamic and engaging learning experience.

Furthermore, the positive student responses reflect a genuine interest and comfort in learning with the module. The structured language and clarity in delivery were repeatedly mentioned as strengths, making it easier for students to absorb the material without feeling overwhelmed. One student remarked, "In my opinion, the module used is not boring; it is easy for me to understand with structured language delivery" (31 March 2020, Zoom Meet, 19.00-21.00 WIB). This statement underscores the module's effectiveness in presenting complex concepts in an accessible format, which not only made learning enjoyable but also supported sustained engagement with the content. Many students also acknowledged the value of a TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) framework in the module, which combines content with technology to deepen understanding. A student expressed this sentiment by stating, "It is very important to increase content knowledge systematically and in depth by using technology to integrate it into the learning process" (31 March 2020, Zoom Meet, 19.00-21.00 WIB). Such responses highlight the module's success in addressing the diverse learning needs of students while fostering an integrated approach to technology and content learning.

Notably, the module has received positive feedback and high satisfaction ratings, demonstrating its effectiveness in the classroom. The data reveal that the module is successfully implemented and suitable as a benchmark for future instructional practices. The results of students' self-reports, presented in Figure 1, further support the module's positive impact and suitability as a teaching tool.

Figure 1. results of students' self-reports

Despite the overwhelmingly positive response, some students suggested minor adjustments to optimize the TPACK elements within the module. While the module is already effective, these insights provide valuable direction for further refinement, ensuring that future implementations maximize learning outcomes. This feedback is significant not only for the researchers but also for educators who can apply these insights to other learning modules. The constructive comments gathered from students are essential for continuous improvement, enabling the development of even more effective TPACK-based modules. These findings serve as an important foundation for future module enhancements, paving the way for a more robust and versatile approach to integrating technology into teaching, especially in the rapidly evolving field of E-Business Technology.

Student understanding was measured using pre-test and post-test instruments. The pre-test instrument was administered in the first session through a written assessment, accompanied by the distribution of the Lesson Plan (RPS) and other course guidelines (including a course contract). This pre-test served as a baseline to gauge students' initial understanding before implementing the TPACK-based framework. Initial data were collected through written questions specifically designed around E-Business Technology content, providing a foundation to assess knowledge improvement. These results, detailed in Figure 2 of this article, offer insight into how understanding progresses through the course.

The TPACK-based module was strategically designed to enhance students' comprehension of the material. The measured increase in understanding reflects the module's success in achieving its intended learning outcomes, underscoring the effective implementation of the TPACK framework.

Based on the analysis of students' pre-test and post-test results, it can be concluded that the TPACK framework-based learning module provides a positive boost for students. This module meets the C-2 Understanding level of Bloom's taxonomy, demonstrating its effectiveness as a critical resource for students to master the provided material. Through this module, students are also able to associate the taught content with relevant real-world applications, facilitating deeper connections between theoretical knowledge and practical use. Thus, the integration of TPACK within the E-Business Technology module proves to be effective in building students' understanding and comprehension.

After the module was implemented, 33 students provided feedback, as they were the primary target of the learning module designed for success in the E-Business Technology course. The results from the student responses to the administered questionnaire indicate that the learning module received positive feedback and is deemed suitable as teaching material for learning activities. The overall assessment across both evaluation categories was rated very good.

No	Respondent	Pre Test Score	Post Test Score	Result
1	Res 01	70	87	Improvement
2	Res 02	65	85	Improvement
3	Res 03	80	87	Improvement
4	Res 04	70	84	Improvement
5	Res 05	85	92	Improvement
6	Res 06	60	81	Improvement
7	Res 07	55	90	Improvement
8	Res 08	65	87	Improvement
9	Res 09	65	83	Improvement
10	Res 10	70	93	Improvement
11	Res 11	65	91	Improvement
12	Res 12	65	92	Improvement
13	Res 13	75	90	Improvement
14	Res 14	80	90	Improvement
15	Res 15	85	88	Improvement
16	Res 16	65	92	Improvement
17	Res 17	75	84	Improvement
18	Res 18	85	85	Improvement
19	Res 19	85	88	Improvement
20	Res 20	75	91	Improvement
21	Res 21	65	86	Improvement
22	Res 22	75	88	Improvement
23	Res 23	65	90	Improvement
24	Res 24	75	91	Improvement
25	Res 25	85	90	Improvement
26	Res 26	65	90	Improvement
27	Res 27	75	85	Improvement
28	Res 28	60	91	Improvement
29	Res 29	60	84	Improvement
30	Res 30	80	88	Improvement
31	Res 31	85	84	Improvement
32	Res 32	80	91	Improvement
33	Res 33	65	82	Improvement

Figure 2. Pre-Test and Post-Test Results of Student Understanding

The researcher also observed the continuity of classroom activities while students utilized the learning module. Generally, the learning activities aligned well with the expected educational outcomes. Students were able to enhance their skills through direct practice by implementing the material included in the learning module. One noteworthy response from the respondents highlighted the use of barcodes that integrate online materials. This barcode feature was utilized to support a deeper understanding of the content. A student remarked, “In my opinion, the module is good; the sentences are straightforward, and with the QR Code, we can explore more extensive materials available on YouTube and articles, providing a fun new learning experience” (March 31, 2020, Zoom Meet, 19:00-21:00 WIB).

The abundance of positive responses from students regarding the learning module indicates that they felt comfortable and enjoyed learning through the provided resources. Another student stated, “I find the module engaging; it is easy for me to understand due to the structured language used” (March 31, 2020, Zoom Meet, 19:00-21:00 WIB). Feedback on the development and implementation of the TPACK-based module fell within a good category, with students emphasizing the importance of systematically and deeply enhancing content knowledge through the integration of technology into the learning process.

Overall, student responses were quite varied, but students generally felt supported and found the module easy to understand as a teaching resource. However, some components require further adjustments to optimize the application of the TPACK concept within the module. This observation serves as an important note for educators in general. The findings will provide a basis for future improvements, allowing those focused in this field to address any shortcomings.

Discussion

The module plays a crucial role in supporting educators in delivering material effectively and within the intended context (Kuncahyono, 2018). By providing structured content, the module allows educators to explain the role of technology with minimal intervention, reducing the over-reliance on technology itself. Additionally, the TPACK framework helps shape the thinking processes and scientific mindset of both educators and learners, fostering a more cohesive understanding of content and technology integration (Peter, 2023).

Figure 2 reveals that 33 students participated in the learning process. The data shows a highest pre-test score of 85, which increased to 92 in the post-test. The lowest pre-test score was 60, while the lowest post-test score reached 84. All respondents demonstrated improved understanding, with the average score rising from 71.9 to 87.87. This indicates that implementing the TPACK framework in the E-Business Technology module contributed significantly to enhancing students' skills. These results align with Vivianti (Vivianti, 2012), who found that a structured module could significantly improve students' comprehension in Information and Communication Technology. Similarly, Huda

(2017) demonstrated that TPACK-based modules effectively enhance students' understanding of more complex topics, such as the Fundamentals of Thermodynamics. This analysis highlights that TPACK-based modules substantially support students' comprehension across foundational, intermediate, and complex subject matter.

The module plays a crucial role in supporting educators in delivering content relevant to E-Business by substituting technology and assisting in explaining concepts with minimal face-to-face interaction. Students can effectively interpret the material through the module, and the TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) framework aids in constructing the necessary thinking framework for both educators and learners (Peter, 2023). The E-Business Technology module addresses the technological engagement gap in specific subject areas. TPACK encompasses the knowledge of appropriately using technology within suitable pedagogical frameworks to effectively teach specific content, allowing educators to master the essential elements needed to navigate diverse technological tools in learning environments. The module has received positive feedback, demonstrating its effectiveness as a reliable benchmark for implementation.

TPACK significantly contributes to interpreting the E-Business module in terms of content, language, presentation, and graphics, enhancing its organization and comprehension. The integration of CK (Content Knowledge), PK (Pedagogical Knowledge), TK (Technological Knowledge), TPK (Technological Pedagogical Knowledge), and PCK (Pedagogical Content Knowledge) enriches the learning experience by interconnecting teaching, scholarship, technology, strategies, and insights. This comprehensive integration highlights a measurable learning orientation. While TPACK offers extensive opportunities for creating enriched modules tailored to student needs, it can only be realized when the three primary aspects—CK, PK, and TK—are fulfilled. This study not only provides a reference for educators to apply the TPACK framework in specific subjects but also contributes to the research field as a valuable resource for future applications, enhancing mastery of E-Business material and guiding informed decisions in teaching practices. Ultimately, educators must determine the most effective media and strategies for their instructional goals.

Conclusion

The analysis concludes that the learning module is highly effective, making it a valuable resource for teaching E-Business Technology. The pre-test and post-test analysis indicates a significant improvement in student understanding, with the average score rising from 71.9 to 87.87, surpassing the minimum mastery criterion of 75 for the course. This suggests that the integration of TPACK within the module is effective in enhancing student comprehension. While students generally find the module supportive and easy to understand, some aspects require refinement to better align with the TPACK concept.

The research findings yield both theoretical and practical implications. The TPACK-based module effectively facilitates students' comprehension of complex information, underscoring the critical role of learning modules as educational tools. A TPACK-based module allows educators to interpret content according to the three fundamental components required for student learning—Content Knowledge, Technological Knowledge, and Pedagogical Knowledge. Integrating the TPACK approach in the E-Business Technology module enables educators to convey complex information effectively, enhancing student understanding. This approach equips students to effectively apply and transfer knowledge gained through TPACK-based modules.

From a practical standpoint, teaching materials play a crucial role in preparing educational content for instructors. This approach reduces educators' workloads by minimizing the need for direct explanations of complex details. This method not only alleviates the teaching burden but also enables instructors to focus on other preparatory tasks outside of teaching, making it accessible for novice teachers with limited experience. It is essential for both educators and module editors to incorporate the TPACK framework as a means of conveying educational messages effectively. The government should provide resources such as digital tools and training programs to promote student independence and strengthen the overall educational system. Future development of TPACK-based modules for the E-Business Technology course is recommended to enhance student literacy, and further research should explore developing TPACK modules that align with competencies aimed at preparing educators for the 21st century.

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